

CERTIFICATE OF APPRECIATION

THIS CERTIFIES THAT
TAFAKKUR MANZILI
JURNALIDA FAOL ISHTIROK ETGANI UCHUN

Babajanova Mohira Rajabboyevna

KREATIVLIK VA UNING DARS JARAYONIDAGI AHAMIYATI

NOMLI MAQOLASI BILAN ISHTIROK ETGANI UCHUN TAQDIRLANADI

2023/FEVRAL

